

ISSUES OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION OF THE ECONOMY IN OUR UZBEKISTAN

Shadiyeva Gulnora Mardiyevna

SamISI, professor of the Department of Real Economy

Asrorov Uchkun Akram ugli

SamISI, Master of the Faculty of Economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7551751>

Abstract: The article aims to find a solution to the urgent issues facing our Republic today, the theoretical and practical approaches to the development of "Entrepreneurship in the conditions of digitalization of the economy in our country", the directions of its application in innovative processes, and the implementation of new directions of the economic development of our country based on foreign experience is dedicated to giving suggestions and recommendations for improvement.

Key words: Digital entrepreneurship, Innovation, Virtual environment, Digital technologies, Digital service, Innovative entrepreneurship, Business entities.

ВОПРОСЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ ЭКОНОМИКИ В НАШЕМ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация: В статье ставится задача найти решение актуальных вопросов, стоящих сегодня перед нашей республикой, теоретические и практические подходы к развитию «Предпринимательства в условиях цифровизации экономики в нашей стране», направления его применения в инновационных процессах, а реализации новых направлений экономического развития нашей страны на основе зарубежного опыта посвящена даче предложений и рекомендаций по совершенствованию.

Ключевые слова: Цифровое предпринимательство, Инновации, Виртуальная среда, Цифровые технологии, Цифровой сервис, Инновационное предпринимательство, Субъекты хозяйствования.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in the conditions of digitization of the economy in our country, the development of entrepreneurship and the development of the lifestyle of the population are becoming an important issue on the agenda. The role of small business and private entrepreneurship is incomparable to build a new Uzbekistan in accordance with the requirements of the times. As the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: "It is necessary to give priority to the support of entrepreneurial initiatives related to the solution of social problems in localities, especially the entrepreneurship of young people and women. For this purpose, a wide path will be opened to the population and entrepreneurs, to microfinance services and financial resources, and to public purchases. Through such measures our people's passion and confidence to become entrepreneurs will increase, they will strive to earn more income."¹

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It can be seen that one of the many directions of entrepreneurship development is the problems related to the development and improvement of efficiency of small business and private entrepreneurship in the conditions of digitalization of the economy." Digital technologies not only increase the quality of products but also their services, moreover, it can be a sufficient reason for

¹ Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. 2020 year

reducing excess costs. At the same time, it is also an effective tool in eradicating the worst evil that worries and disturbs me the most - the scourge of corruption. "These words of the President are significant because digitization not only ensures savings and efficiency in economic sectors, but is also noted as an effective tool for fighting corruption. In the same way, in the era of the digital economy, we can see that the problems in the development of entrepreneurship will be solved without corruption, and new additional opportunities will be presented to our entrepreneurs.

It should be noted that during the pandemic, about 20 decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan were adopted to support entrepreneurship. With these decrees and decisions, legal economic and financial opportunities were created in order to support entrepreneurship and service industries. Decree No. PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the spending strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "Every family-entrepreneur" dated June 7, 2018, the decision of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 9, 2018, on the approval of the regulation on the procedure for allocating loans within the program "Every family-entrepreneur"² and other research serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks defined in the normative legal documents.

This indicates the relevance of the chosen topic. In particular, the procedures for state registration of business activities, obtaining various permits, and many other services have been simplified. In order to facilitate this, the State Services Agency and its local centers were established. The position of business ombudsman has been introduced. Reception offices of the Prime Minister were established in all regions, which receive and help resolve businessmen's appeals. Under the Cabinet of Ministers, the activities of the State Fund to Support the Development of Entrepreneurship were launched, and 200 billion sums and 50 million dollars were allocated to it³. GDP per capital in January-June 2022 at current prices was 10,994.9 thousand sums (or the equivalent of 995.3 US dollars) and increased by 3.3% compared to January-June 2021. Sd. In recent years, as a result of the reforms carried out in our republic, the number of small business entities (without farms and peasant farms) is increasing (diagram 1).

Diagram 1

² <https://lex.uz/docs/4818719>

³ Presidential Decree on the introduction of a new system for the development of small business and entrepreneurship 10.03.2022

As can be seen from the data presented in the diagram above, in 2018 there were 257,127 small business entities (excluding farmers and peasant farms), 323,014 in 2019, 391,300 in 2020, 472,273 in 2021, and 509,720 by 2022. and increased by 2.0 times compared to the corresponding period of 2018.

In addition, we can analyze how the share of small business and private entrepreneurship in our country has changed from 2019 to the 3rd quarter of 2022 in the areas of the following table 1⁴. Namely:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Share of small business and private entrepreneurship in our country

Table 1

Statistics	2019	2020	2021	2022Q2	2022Q3
GDP	56.0	55.7	54.9	50.5	52.8
Industry	25.8	27.9	27.0	23.2	24.2
Construction	75.8	72.5	72.4	74.9	73.8
Employment	76.2	74.5	74.4	74.8	-
Export	27.0	20.5	22.3	17.6	27.4
Import	61.6	51.7	48.7	44.7	48.8

It can be seen from the table above that there was a small decrease in the business of the GDP sector compared to 2019. But the import sector has decreased by almost 12% compared to 2019 by the 3rd quarter of 2022, and the share of the import sector is 48.8%. It can be said that the rest of the sectors kept their shares almost unchanged compared to 2019.

CONCLUSION

In short, the following can be achieved by gradually, systematically and continuously improving the organizational economic mechanisms of small business and private entrepreneurship development. Managing and developing sectors of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including private entrepreneurship, in a digitalized way is one of the most urgent tasks set by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev. It is our country to develop entrepreneurship.

It is an important condition for improving the living conditions of citizens, reducing poverty, and achieving economic development. Today, the growth of population income in the developed countries of the world is primarily due to the correct organization of innovative processes in entrepreneurship and the continuous improvement of digital entrepreneurship. One of the important tasks facing our republic in the context of the formation of a digital economy is to expand the production of products and the provision of services that are competitive in the world market.

Today, one of the main tasks is to reduce prices by ensuring healthy competition among entrepreneurs and to expand the production of export-quality products that are competitive in the world market. Studying the international experience, it is necessary to open a wider path for the private sector to monopoly areas, develop "digital entrepreneurship" and thereby create a competitive environment.

⁴ State Statistics Committee

REFERENCES:

1. Mirziyoyev.Sh.M Erkin va farovon,demokratik O'zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz.—Toshkent.2016.,15-bet
2. Yuldashev D.T. Oilaviy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish. Dic ... i.f. bo'yicha falcafa doktori (PhD). – T., 2019;
3. G'oyipnazarov C.B. Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikda mehnatni muhofaza qilishning ilmiy acolarini takomillashtirish. Dic. ... i.f. bo'yicha falcafa doktori (PhD). – T.
4. Shakirova, F. B. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF INVESTMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATION IN THE ECONOMY. *Confrencea*, 7(7), 61-62.
5. Shakirova, F. B. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF TAXES IN BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT. *Confrencea*, 6(6), 236-237.
6. FB, A. S. S., & Shonazarova, N. B. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF INVESTMENT ACTIVITIES IN THE RAILWAY TRANSPORT NETWORK IN UZBEKISTAN. *Confrencea*, 6(6), 216-217.
7. Sattorova, F. S. S. (2022). STRATEGY OF ENTERING INTERNATIONAL MARKETS OF" UZBEKISTAN RAILWAYS" JSC INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES. *Confrencea*, 5(5), 101-106.
8. Шакирова, Ф. Б. (2022). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА НА ОСНОВЕ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(2), 382-390.